

IMPORTANCE OF OCCUPATIONAL HYGIENE IN WORKPLACES

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses issues such as the standard system of labor safety, general issues of labor protection, labor hygiene and industrial sanitation, sanitary norms and rules, technical safety, fire safety.

INTRODUCTION

Occupational hygiene, occupational hygiene is a branch of hygiene. He studies the impact of labor processes and production environment on the human body and develops hygiene standards and measures to create comfortable working conditions and prevent occupational diseases. Har. working conditions in any place depend on the technology of the production process and the sanitary and hygienic conditions created in the workplace. In the process of physical work, it mainly affects human muscles, and in physical work, it is great from the nervous and mental side. As technology developed and production processes were perfected, physical work was replaced by mental work, and there was a need to learn more about mental work processes.

Sanitary and hygienic conditions of labor hygiene means the entire situation around the worker, including chemicals, dust, noise, vibration, ionizing rays, as well as air temperature, humidity, speed of movement, lighting of rooms or other workplaces, abundance of microorganisms and understood differently. Each or several of these factors together can cause health damage unless appropriate protective measures are taken. The main task of occupational hygiene is to prevent these negative effects. Improvement of working conditions is a national task in the Republic of Uzbekistan. According to the "Regulation on State Sanitary Control of the Republic of Uzbekistan", the main task of state sanitary control in the field of labor hygiene is to monitor compliance with sanitary laws.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

Various methods are used for control in occupational hygiene. The most important of these are sanitary and hygiene inspections. Weather-related factors; this method is used in measuring the level of air pollution, vibration, noise, radioactive rays and other works. In addition, there are physiological, statistical and experimental methods of investigation. Occupational hygiene also studies the laws of interaction between the organism and the production environment in order to determine the hygiene regulations that are most consistent with the physiological and biological requirements of the human body in production. According to the procedure introduced in the country, none of the production factors should exceed the permissible norm or maximum concentration, and the factors should not cause certain diseases or any significant changes to those people when workers are close to them for an unlimited period of time. Occupational hygiene is carried out in accordance with special state regulations, guidelines and instructions developed and recommended by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan¹.

Labor protection is socio-economic, organizational, technical, sanitary-hygiene and treatment-prophylactic measures aimed at ensuring the safety, health and working capacity of a person in the labor process, acting on the basis of the relevant law and other regulatory documents, and consists of a system of tools. Working conditions envisage a set of technical and organizational measures that ensure the rational use of labor force. Measures to improve working conditions have a great impact on the final results of work, development of social production and increase of its efficiency.

If the work performed in production corresponds to the first category of labor intensity according to psychophysiological criteria, if the production environment according to sanitary-hygiene criteria is in accordance with the established norms, if it meets modern requirements and recommendations according to aesthetic criteria, if a favorable environment is created among employees that ensures compliance with the rules of technical safety and labor protection according to social and psychological criteria, such conditions can be considered as the most optimal working conditions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The International Labor Organization (ILO), which is a member of 178 countries of the world, plays a key role in setting international standards of labor, including labor protection. International legal standards on the most important issues of social protection of the employee in the course of work are defined in the conventions and recommendations of the International Labor Organization. In general, more than a third of the more than 300 conventions and recommendations of the International Labor Organization are directly or indirectly related to the problems of labor protection and occupational hygiene, and more than 40 normative documents directly - dedicated to the problems of proper labor protection.

Hygiene services perform the following functions:

- identification of factors that have a dangerous effect on health that appear at the workplace and assessment of this risk;
- establishing control over factors of the production environment and production operations that have an adverse effect on the health of employees.

¹ Abdurakhmanov O.K. Improving the efficiency of management of the labor protection system in the Republic of Uzbekistan. T.: Fan., 2010. – 326 p.

The hygiene service participates in the organization of primary and emergency medical care, the analysis of industrial accidents and occupational diseases, as well as the implementation of occupational rehabilitation measures. It works in cooperation with enterprise services and medical institutions. Professionally independent personnel with appropriate qualifications providing services in the field of occupational hygiene. In situations related to the labor process, monitoring of the state of health of employees will not be at the expense of their wages, that is, it will be carried out free of charge and during working hours to the extent possible.

Legislation aimed at improving working conditions and the production environment is increasingly directed towards the goal of implementing extensive preventive measures that provide for the comfort of human labor. In this place, first of all, it is intended to create conditions that meet the physical and mental abilities of employees as fully as possible, to achieve a safe and healthy production environment. For this purpose, ergonomic principles are used in the design of machines and work organization, and special attention is paid to the prevention of overstrain of employees. In the event that an employee is diagnosed with an occupational disease in the course of a medical examination, the medical commission of this employee shall refer the employee to the Institute of Sanitation, Hygiene and Occupational Diseases of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Tashkent. should be sent to the appropriate clinics of the medical academy.

The collective agreement may include the following obligations of employers and employees in the field of working conditions and labor protection²:

- measures to eliminate air pollution in workplaces where free milk is provided, measures to make working conditions fully compliant with sanitary and hygienic regulations and rules;
- timely delivery of comfortable and modern special clothing, shoes and other personal protective equipment, as well as personal hygiene items;
- carrying out their expertise in order to determine the impact of working conditions on the health of employees, etc.

CONCLUSION

Scientifically based labor standards and regulations are designed for a certain concrete situation based on advanced production (service) experiences. Therefore, in addition to studying and monitoring the use of working time by employees, organization, planning, design, service, equipment and equipment, specialization, labor safety and sanitary-hygienic conditions, work and rest procedures are also necessary. will be studied in detail. Studying the state of the workplace provides an opportunity to develop and introduce elements of work organization, provides information for normalizing the amount of work time required for rest, and determines requirements for the design of workplaces.

Assessment of the compliance of working conditions with hygiene regulations is carried out by measuring and evaluating the levels of production and labor process factors with tools during the implementation of state production (technological) processes and (or) state activities of the enterprise. In the assessment, the methods stipulated in the normative legal documents and other documents, as well as the measuring instruments checked in the

² Abdurakhmanov K.Kh. Labor economy: theory and practice. T., 2014. 34 p.

prescribed manner, should be used. The assessment of compliance of working conditions with hygiene regulations is carried out according to the criteria determined by the hygiene classification of working conditions according to indicators of harmfulness and danger of factors of the production environment, severity and seriousness of the labor process.

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